

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SANITATION PRACTICES AMONG RESIDENTS OF YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE

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Abstract: This study examined the knowledge, attitude and environmental sanitation practices among residents of Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. A descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted for this study. The population of this study was 239, 200 with a sample size of 440 residents using Yaro Yamene method. A multi-stage sampling procedure was implemented for the study in two stages. The instrument for collection of data was a self-structured questionnaire titled the Knowledge and Environmental Sanitation Practices Questionnaire (KESPOQ). The validated instrument was considered reliable as the reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Data collected was analysed using Statistical Products for Service Solutions (SPSS) version 27.0. The result showed that more of the respondents 301(71.2%) had good knowledge of environmental sanitation in Yenagoa LGA. The result of the overall score showed that 378(89.4%) had positive attitude while 45(10.6%) had negative attitude towards environmental sanitation. The result of the overall score showed that 395(93.4%) had good level of practice while 28(6.6%) had poor level of practice. Thus, the level of environmental sanitation practice among residents was good. The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between gender, educational level, socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ ($p = 0.08$). The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.02$). The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.02$). The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between socioeconomic status, educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ ($p = 0.36$ & $p = 0.27$). The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ ($p = 0.00$). The result also showed that there was a statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and practice environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ ($p =$

o.oo). It was concluded that residents had good knowledge, attitude and environmental sanitation practices. The increase in knowledge, positive attitude and practices of environmental sanitation varied in gender, socioeconomic status, educational level. The result of this study also concluded that demographic variables were associated affecting with environmental sanitation practice. This study recommended among others that community leaders and stakeholders should mobilize the members of the community to practice good sanitation activities such weekly or monthly sanitation programs.

Introduction

Sanitation practices have seen as global means of preventing parasitic infectious diseases both in developed and developing countries including Nigeria. Sanitation is a global development priority and the subject of Sustainable Development Goal 6. The estimate in 2017 by the World Health Organization states that 4.5 billion people currently do not have safely managed sanitation (World Health Organization, 2017). Lack of access to sanitation has an impact not only on public health but also on human dignity and personal safety. It is estimated that up to 5 million people die each year from preventable waterborne diseases, including Children as a result of inadequate sanitation and hygiene practices (United Nations World Water Assessment Programme, 2017). The effect of sanitation has impacted the society of people throughout history. Hence, sanitation is a necessity for healthy living. However, it is estimated that 2.4 billion people still lacked improved sanitation facilities as of 2015 (Duncan, 2017).

Sanitation refers to public health conditions related to clean drinking water and adequate treatment and disposal of human excreta and sewage, Preventing human contact with faeces is part of sanitation, as is hand washing with soap

(Oxford Dictionaries, 2017). Sanitation systems aim to protect human health by providing a clean environment that will stop the transmission of disease, especially through the faecal–oral route (WHO, 2017). For example, diarrhea, a main cause of malnutrition and stunted growth in children, can be reduced through sanitation. There are many other diseases which are easily transmitted in communities that have low levels of sanitation, such as ascariasis (a type of intestinal worm infection or helminthiasis), cholera, hepatitis, polio, schistosomiasis, trachoma, to name just a few (United Nation Children Fund, 2017).

For any social and economic development, adequate sanitation in conjunction with good hygiene and safe water are essential to good health. Lack of proper sanitation causes diseases. Most of the diseases resulting from sanitation have a direct relation to poverty. The lack of clean water and poor sanitation causes many diseases and the spread of diseases. It is estimated that inadequate sanitation is responsible for 4.0 percent of deaths and 5.7 percent of disease burden worldwide (Tilley, et al, 2014). Lack of sanitation is a serious issue that is affecting most developing countries and countries in transition. The importance of the isolation of excreta and waste lies in an effort to

prevent diseases which can be transmitted through human waste, which afflict both developed countries as well as developing countries to differing degrees.

Apparently, Flores (2010) noted that this situation presents substantial public health risks as the waste could contaminate drinking water and cause life-threatening forms of diarrhoea to infants. Improved sanitation, including hand washing and water purification, could save the lives of 1.5 million children who die from diarrheal diseases each year. For example, deaths resulting from diarrhea are estimated to be between 1.6 and 2.5 million deaths every year (Duncan, 2017). Most of the affected are young children below the ages of five. Children suffering from diarrhea are more vulnerable to become underweight (due to stunted growth) which makes them more vulnerable to other diseases such as acute respiratory infections and malaria. In many settings, provision of sanitation facilities alone does not guarantee good health of the population. Studies have suggested that the impact of hygiene practices have as great an impact on sanitation related diseases as the actual provision of sanitation facilities. Hygiene promotion is therefore an important part of sanitation and is usually key in maintaining good health (Jon, 2017). Hygiene practice or promotion is a planned approach of enabling people to act and change their behaviour in an order to reduce and/or prevent incidences of water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) related diseases. It usually involves a participatory approach of engaging people to take responsibility of WASH services and infrastructure including its operation and maintenance. The three key elements of promoting hygiene are; mutual sharing of

information and knowledge, the mobilisation of affected communities and the provision of essential material and facilities (World Health Organization, 2017).

In Nigeria, waste disposal, refuse disposal as well as inadequate water supply are problems in the environment especially in secondary schools. It is caused by a lot of factors. These includes neglect of the operation and maintenance of health facilities, lack of hygiene education for the students, non-existent or insufficient water supply, poor sanitation and inadequate hand washing facilities, dirty and unsafe water supply; toilets or latrines that are not adapted to the needs of students as well as unhealthy and dirty classrooms/school compounds (Joro, 2009). These factors have led to consequences on student health. Diseases related to poor sanitation and water availability causes many sicknesses like cholera, diarrhoea, malaria and typhoid. All these diseases greatly affect the health of students. Students cannot even learn properly because they are sick. Even learning in unhealthy environments leads to student not even understanding what they are being taught and in extreme cases it could lead to students' mortality.

Based on the negative effects of poor sanitation on the health of students, it is not clear on the extent in which school management and parents have contributed in curbing poor sanitation practices. Hence, if students have good knowledge of environmental sanitation and the diseases associated with poor practices, it will help them to practice proper environmental sanitation in their various schools and home. A lot of literature available talks about environmental sanitation strategies but most of them have been done in the wider communities

and not in institutions of learning. Therefore, the study seeks to investigate knowledge, attitude and environmental sanitation practices among residents in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Hypotheses

In regards to this study, the following hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.
4. There is no significant association between educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.
5. There is no significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State?
6. There is no significant association between socioeconomic status and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.
7. There is no significant association between educational level and environmental sanitation practices among residents of Bayelsa State?

8. There is no significant association between gender and environmental sanitation practices among residents of Bayelsa State.

9. There is no significant association between socioeconomic status and environmental sanitation practices among residents of Bayelsa State.

Methodology

Study Area: Bayelsa state is one the major states south-south geopolitical zone that was create in 1996 under the military regime of Gen. Sani Abacha. There are eight local government areas which includes Brass, Ekeremor, Kolga, Nembe, Ogbia, Sagbama, Kolga, Southern Ijaw and Yenagoa as the headquarters of Bayelsa state and several ministries in the civil service commission.

Study design: descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted for this study. This design carefully describes, explain and analyse the experience.

Population of the Study: The population of this study of residents in Yenagoa Local Government Area in this was two hundred and thirty nine thousand two hundred (239, 200) (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Sample and sampling techniques: The sample size of the study was 440 residents which was estimated using Yaro Yamene method for finite population.

$$\text{Formula: } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

N = total number of population from Yenagoa Local Government Area.

n = sample size

e = level of significance (0.05)

A multi-stage sampling procedure will be implemented for the study in two stages. Stage

one: Simple random sampling technique was used to select 10 communities from 20 communities in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. This was done by balloting without replacement. Stage two: systematic sampling technique was employed to select 44 residents from each selected communities in Yenagoa Local Government Area to make up the sample.

Method for Data Collection: The instrument for collection of data was a self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire titled the Knowledge and Environmental Sanitation Practices Questionnaire (KESPQ) which comprised of section A, B, C and D respectively.

Reliability of the Instrument: The instrument was considered reliable as the

Table 1.1: Chi-square test showing association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Education	Level of Knowledge			Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Good F (%)	Average F (%)	Poor F (%)					
None	31(10.3)	6(11.1)	2(2.9)	39(9.2)	6	11.57	0.07*	H ₀ not rejected
Primary	20(6.6)	0(0.00)	7(10.3)	27(6.4)				
Secondary	61(20.3)	9(16.7)	9(13.2)	79(18.7)				
Tertiary	189(62.8)	39(72.2)	50(73.5)	278(65.7)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	68(100)	423(100)				

*Not significant, $p > 0.05$

Table 1.1 showed the Chi-square test of association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 11.57, df = 6, $p = 0.07$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no

reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained using Pearson Product moment correlation.

Method for Data Analysis: Data collected was analyzed using Statistical Products for Service Solutions (SPSS) version 27.0. Descriptive statistical tools such as frequency count, percentage, and inferential statistical tool such as Chi-Square test were employed test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: There is no significant association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

significant association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.2: Chi-square test showing association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Gender	Level of Knowledge			Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Good F (%)	Average F (%)	Poor F (%)					
Male	132(43.9)	27(50.0)	26(38.2)	185(43.7)	2	1.69	0.42*	H ₀ not rejected
Female	169(56.1)	27(50.0)	42(61.8)	238(56.3)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	68(100)	423(100)				

*Not significant, $p > 0.05$

Table 1.2 showed the Chi-square test of association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 1.69, df = 2, $p = 0.42$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated

that there is no significant association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.3: Chi-square test showing association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Socioeconomic status	Level of Knowledge			Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Good F (%)	Average F (%)	Poor F (%)					
>30,000	143(47.5)	15(27.8)	37(54.4)	195(46.1)	6	11.03	0.08*	H ₀ not rejected
<30,000	89(29.6)	21(38.9)	17(25.0)	127(30.0)				
None	67(22.3)	18(33.3)	13(19.1)	98(23.2)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	68(100)	423(100)				

*Not significant, $p > 0.05$

Table 1.3 showed the Chi-square test of association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 11.03, df = 6, $p = 0.08$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there

is no significant association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant association between educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.4: Chi-square test showing association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Education	Attitude		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Positive F (%)	Negative F (%)					
None	35(9.3)	4(8.9)	39(9.2)	3	9.79	0.02*	H ₀ Rejected
Primary	27(7.1)	0(0.00)	27(6.4)				
Secondary	76(20.1)	3(6.7)	79(18.7)				
Tertiary	240(63.5)	38(84.4)	278(65.7)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	423(100)				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Table 1.4 showed the Chi-square test of association between educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 9.79, df = 3, $p = 0.02$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no

significant association between educational level and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis Five: There is no significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.5: Chi-square test showing association between gender and attitude toward environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Gender	Attitude		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Positive F (%)	Negative F (%)					
Male	159(42.1)	26(57.8)	185(43.7)	1	4.03	0.04*	H ₀ Rejected
Female	219(57.9)	19(42.2)	238(56.3)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	423(100)				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Table 1.5 showed the Chi-square test of association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between gender and attitude

towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 9.79, df = 3, $p = 0.02$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis Six: There is no significant association between socioeconomic status and

attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.6: Chi-square test showing association between socioeconomic status and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Gender	Attitude		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Positive F (%)	Negative F (%)					
>30,000	171(45.2)	24(53.3)	195(46.1)	3	3.21	0.36*	H ₀ Not Rejected
<30,000	112(29.6)	15(33.3)	127(30.0)				
None	92(24.3)	6(13.3)	98(23.2)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	423(100)				

*Not Significant, $p > 0.05$

Table 1.6 showed the Chi-square test of association between socioeconomic status and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 3.21, df = 3, $p = 0.36$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no

significant association between socioeconomic status and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Seven: There is no significant association between educational level and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.7: Chi-square test showing association between educational level and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Education	Practice		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Good F (%)	Poor F (%)					
None	39(9.9)	0(0.00)	39(9.2)	3	3.85	0.27*	H ₀ not rejected
Primary	25(6.3)	2(7.1)	27(6.4)				
Secondary	75(19.0)	4(14.3)	79(18.7)				
Tertiary	256(64.8)	22(78.6)	278(65.7)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	423(100)				

*Not Significant, $p > 0.05$

Table 1.7 showed the Chi-square test of association between educational level and practice of environmental sanitation among

residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between educational level and

practice of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 3.85, $df = 3$, $p = 0.27$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant association between educational level and practice of environmental sanitation

among residents of Bayelsa State was not rejected.

Hypothesis Eight: There is no significant association between gender and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.8: Chi-square test showing association between gender and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Gender	Practice		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Good F (%)	Poor F (%)					
Male	183(46.3)	2(7.1)	185(43.7)	1	16.31	0.00*	H ₀ Rejected
Female	212(53.7)	26(92.9)	238(56.3)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	423(100)				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Table 1.8 showed the Chi-square test of association between gender and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 16.31, $df = 1$, $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated

that there is no significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis Nine: There is no significant association between socioeconomic status and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.9: Chi-square test showing association between socioeconomic status and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State

Gender	Practice		Total	df	χ^2	p-value	Decision
	Good F (%)	Poor F (%)					
>30,000	191(48.4)	4(14.3)	195(46.1)	3	16.43	0.00*	H ₀ Rejected
<30,000	117(29.6)	10(35.7)	127(30.0)				
None	84(21.3)	14(50.0)	98(23.2)				
Total	301(100)	54(100)	423(100)				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Table 1.9 showed the Chi-square test of association between socioeconomic status and

practice towards environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State. The result

showed that there was a statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and practice environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 16.43, df = 3, $p = 0.00$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant association between socioeconomic status and practice of environmental sanitation among residents of Bayelsa State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study were discussed below:

Knowledge of Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that more of the respondents 301(71.2%) had good knowledge of environmental sanitation, 68(16.1%) had poor knowledge while 54(12.8%) had average level of knowledge. Thus, the level of knowledge about environmental sanitation among residents of Yenagoa LGA was good. The result of this study is expected because public health program through agencies on sanitation may have been done in the Yenagoa and the extent of exposure to information was high that increase the level of knowledge. The result of this study is in line with findings of World Health Organization, (2010) which reported that increase in knowledge about sanitation and its diseases if not attended to demonstrate better practices that aim to promote healthy habits. The result of this findings is in credence with findings of Mbonane and Naicker (2020) which reported the knowledge score of residents ranged from 1-9 having good knowledge of environmental sanitation. Berhe et al. (2020) carried a similar study in Northern Ethiopian on knowledge of sanitation which agreed with this study that more than average number of participants had good knowledge of water, sanitation and hygiene. In Nigeria, Sridhar et al. (2020) affirmed that good proportion of residents knew

about treated water supply for human consumption, toilet facility of excreta disposal and prevent the spread of open defecation. Suting (2016) added that people (43%) have good knowledge on environmental sanitation and its impact on health with a mean score of 28.08 which is in concord with outcome of this present study. Studies of Sibiya and Gumbo (2013) and Joshi et al. (2013) whose findings buttressed that good proportion of residents (45%) had toilet facility established within their household and 53% of them conduct water examination on drinking water before consumption. Msengi and Deo (2017) affirmed that about average number of residents (41%) have high knowledge score of practicing environmental sanitation. In South-West Nigeria, study Adeolu (2015) which revealed the level of knowledge of waste management was relatively moderate in secondary schools in Ibadan. Getachew and Dessalew (2018) reported that good proportion of resident had 60.8%) correct knowledge of environmental sanitation as well as hygiene in Ethiopia. Mohd and Malik (2017) which reported that knowledge revealed that 88.3% respondents attributed sanitation within their surroundings. Prior study in Nigeria, Ebong (2009) reported in Zaria Kaduna State that environmental hygiene, respondents had good knowledge with a score of 61.5%. Aswathy (2015) which illustrated that majority of (57%) residents had average knowledge score of environmental sanitation. It is plausible because those who are exposed to information about environmental sanitation are more likely to have increase of about. As at the time of this study there was no prior findings that contradict with the outcome of this present study. Hence, the knowledge of environmental

sanitation among residents of Yenagoa in Bayelsa state was good.

Educational Level and Knowledge of Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between educational level and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 11.57, $df = 6$, $p = 0.07$). The result of this study is expected because education provide greater insight and understanding about environmental sanitation. The result of this study is in credence with findings of Kanungo et al. (2021) which indicated that over 90% of households knew about benefit of sanitation with regards to the education acquired. Studies of Msengi and Deo (2017) buttressed that resident with at least secondary level of education were 4.39 times more likely to know more about environmental sanitation and was statistically significant. In South-West Nigeria, study Adeolu (2015) which revealed the level of knowledge of waste management was relatively moderate in residents in Ibadan was significantly determine by level of education. Marie-Rosette et al. (2017) which buttressed that 25.9% of the residents had received health education on environmental sanitation. Prior study in Nigeria, Ebong (2009) reported in Zaria Kaduna State that environmental hygiene, respondents had good knowledge based on educational level was 45.8% of the sample. Studies of Ssemugabo, et al. (2019) reported that residents who had attained post primary education are about 2 times more likely to have good knowledge and practice of sanitation as compared with people who have not received any forms of education. Mbonane and Naicker (2020) agreed that educational qualification was significantly

related to good environmental practices among people living in urban areas. Eshete et al. (2023) and Yang et al. (2023) buttressed that residents with higher educational level showed a significantly association regarding knowledge and environmental sanitation practices. Recently, studies of Kanungo et al. (2021) and Berhe et al. (2020) added that sanitation materials and devices are more likely to improve hygiene practices among residents. Such waste disposal material as garbage can, sweeping materials, cleaning materials, and good water supply.

Gender and Knowledge of Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between gender and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 1.69, $df = 2$, $p = 0.42$). The result of this study is in line with findings of Marie-Rosette et al. (2017) which buttressed that 264 (39.3%) males and 407 (60.7%) females are aware of environmental sanitation. Getachew and Dessalew (2018) agreed that significant difference existed between genders based on knowledge of environmental sanitation. Studies of Ssemugabo, et al. (2019) reported that residents who had attained post primary education are about 2 times more likely to have good knowledge and practice of sanitation as compared with people who have not received any forms of education. Mbonane and Naicker (2020) agreed that educational qualification was significantly related to good environmental practices among people living in urban areas. Eshete et al. (2023) and Yang et al. (2023) buttressed that residents with higher educational level showed a significantly association regarding knowledge and

environmental sanitation practices. Recently, studies of Kanungo et al. (2021) and Berhe et al. (2020) added that sanitation materials and devices are more likely to improve hygiene practices among residents. Such waste disposal material as garbage can, sweeping materials, cleaning materials, and good water supply.

Socioeconomic status and Knowledge of Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and knowledge of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 11.03, $df = 6$, $p = 0.08$).

The outcome of this study is in consonance with findings of Mohd and Malik (2017) found a significant association between knowledge and socio-economic status ($\chi^2=8.40$, $p=0.01$). Eshete et al. (2023) supported that income status of the family was significantly associated with availability of sanitation materials requires for hygiene. Raihan et al. (2017) added that socioeconomic status ($p < 0.01$) and WASH ($p < 0.05$) significantly affect sanitation with regards to knowledge. It is plausible that residents with quality standard of living and income status enables them to be eager to sanitation because of exposure to necessary environmental sanitation materials. As at the time of this study, there was no contrary findings against the outcome of this present study. Hence socioeconomic status is a correlates that influence knowledge about environmental sanitation.

Educational level and Attitude towards Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between educational level and attitude towards environmental

sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 9.79, $df = 3$, $p = 0.02$). The result of this study is expected because acquiring good educational background are more likely to cause modification in attitude of people such as residents of Yenagoa L.G.A. The result of this study is in congruence with findings of Yang et al. (2023) which depicted that education level was significantly associated with positive attitude towards of environmental sanitation among residents. It is plausible that those who have received education at all levels would have better understanding and develop familiarity with positive environmental sanitation. As at the time of this study, there was no contrary findings against the outcome of this present study. Hence educational level is a factor that influence attitude towards environmental sanitation.

Gender and Attitude towards Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between gender and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 9.79, $df = 3$, $p = 0.02$). The result of this study is possible because there is variation in the way male and female think and act especially on health related issues. The result of this study is in corroboration with findings of Eshete et al. (2023) which illustrated that 61.3% of women residing in the area believed that environmental sanitation is important to improve the standard of living while (87.4%) of the female households "strongly agreed" about the potential risk associated with improper solid waste disposal and nearly 80% of them also "strongly agreed" that proper SWM is crucial to create a healthy environment in the community. Berhe et al. (2020) affirmed that 75.9% of the respondents were females had good knowledge,

favorable attitude, and good practice on WASH. Findings of Mbonane and Naicker (2020) agreed that good percentage female residents prioritize environmental sanitation such as sweeping, parking of waste and disposal as compared with male counterpart. This study, there was no contrary findings against the outcome of this present study. Hence, gender is a factor that influence attitude towards environmental sanitation

Socioeconomic status and Attitude towards Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and attitude towards environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 3.21, $df = 3$, $p = 0.36$). The result of this study is in credence with findings of Mohd and Malik (2017) which reported that a significant association between attitude and socio-economic status ($\chi^2=8.40$, $p=0.01$) on environmental sanitation among residents. Studies of Yang et al. (2023) depicted that total annual family income ($F=27.977$, $P<0.001$) was a significant predictor of positive attitude regarding environmental sanitation. In North western Nigeria, studies of Sridhar et al. (2020) reported that good proportion of residents from high or medium income background agreed that excreta disposal and safe water supply are good environmental sanitation and hygiene. It is plausible that environmental sanitation as well as hygiene is less possible or inadequately perform in coastal region like Yenagoa L.G.A because it requires availability of sanitation materials that can be purchased using money. Residents from low socioeconomic status would find difficult to accept proper environmental sanitation. This study, there was no contrary findings against the

outcome of this present study. Hence, socio-economic status is a factor that influence attitude towards environmental sanitation.

Educational level and Practice of Environmental Sanitation

The result showed that there was no statistically significant association between educational level and practice of environmental sanitation as $p > 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 3.85, $df = 3$, $p = 0.27$). The result of this study is necessary because education helps to improve and promote good behaviour relating to cleanliness. The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between gender and practice towards environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 16.31, $df = 1$, $p = 0.00$). The result of this study is in credence with findings of Kanungo et al. (2021) which indicated that good proportion of adult women (61%) spent over 20 minutes to perform sanitation practice in their environs. Studies of Mbonane and Naicker (2020) added that educational qualification of resident significantly predict good environmental sanitation practices. It was deduced that education are more likely to bring about a change in attitude and enable individual/family to take positive action in order to improve good health.

Socioeconomic Status and Environmental Sanitation Practice

The result showed that there was a statistically significant association between socioeconomic status and practice environmental sanitation as $p < 0.05$ (X^2 -value = 16.43, $df = 3$, $p = 0.00$). The result of this study is necessary because environmental sanitation is possible and adequately done when residents are able to obtain materials such as broom, packet, and garbage can waste bag among others through

using money to buy. The result of this findings is in agreement with studies of Raihan et al. (2017) which illustrated that socioeconomic status ($p < 0.01$) was statistically significantly with water and sanitation hygiene among residents. The outcome of this study is in consonance with findings of Mohd and Malik (2017) which found a significant association was found between sanitation and hygiene practices and socioeconomic status ($\chi^2 = 18.31$, $p = 0.001$), and family size ($\chi^2 = 13.00$, $p = 0.01$). The outcome of this study may be possible because residents with low income status would not accept and practice sanitation or hygiene adequately due to inability to have essential materials for the environmental sanitation practices. This study, there was no contrary findings against the outcome of this present study. Hence, socioeconomic status is a factor that influence practice towards environmental sanitation.

Conclusion

In regards to the outcome of this findings, it was concluded that residents of Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State had good knowledge, attitude and environmental sanitation practices. The increase in knowledge, positive attitude and practices of environmental sanitation varied in gender, socioeconomic

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status, educational level The result of this study also concluded that demographic variables were associated affecting with environmental sanitation practice.

Recommendations

This study recommended that:

1. Government should enforce sanitation laws and regulation through her environmental sanitation agencies to ensure that residents to have good environmental health status.
2. Families and residents should prioritize their health and that of their environment by ensuring adequate disposal waste to prevent pollution.
3. Community leaders and stakeholders should mobilize the members of the community to practice good sanitation activities such weekly or monthly sanitation programmes.
4. Families and households should be willing to adopt consistent sanitary practices at home such as toilet facility, safe water supply, and domestic waste disposal.
5. Government should ensure that sanitation materials are made available and possibly disclose to the residents especially among residents of low socioeconomic status to enable carry out sanitation activities in their locality.

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